

Test of Arbitrage Pricing Theory: Evidence from Indonesia

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Abstract

This study uses quarterly data, from March 2009 to December 2013 on the 25 liquid stocks listed in the Indonesian Stock Exchange. The data are collected from the Indonesian Capital Market Directory and from the Indonesian Central Bank. The aims from this study are to investigate whether variations in stock returns are sufficiently explained by the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT). To achieve this objective, the study utilized four variables. In addition, the study uses prespecifying macrovariables approach and added gold price as an independent variable. The procedure used a two stage regression. The results indicate that the APT model is quite robust and only inflation and exchange rate have significant and negative effects on the variations in the stock. The theoretical contribution is developing APT which is right for Indonesia and the practical implication is an information for the government to make a policy based on the significant variables and for the investor to be able to consider what factors affect the return share and to prepare to overcome the effect.

Keywords: Liquid stocks, Arbitrage Pricing Theory, prespecifying macrovariables approach.

1. Introduction

The existence of share price fluctuation commercialized to invest in the capital market causes the financiers to develop various models. The initial model which is frequently applied is CAPM model developed by Lintner (1961), Sharpe (1964) and Mossin (1966). However, almost as soon as the CAPM was developed, authors began to find obvious mispriced securities and to question the generality of the theory. (Elton et. al., 1994). CAPM expresses that only a systematic factor can affects return of common stock, that is the return of the market. Later, the next researchers found that there are a lot of factors which affect the share price change.

In the next research was found another model which indicated that there were other factors which affect the return share, among others Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT). APT is a model with many factors. But the weakness of the APT model is that it does not settle the number of factors and does not identify the factors (Tunah, 2013). In the APT model two approaches are used, namely statistical approach and prespecifying macrovariables (Paavola, 2006). Approaches with statistical methods use principle component analysis or factor analysis. The second approach is by settling macroeconomics factors suspected having an effect on to price of share.

This research uses a prespecifying macrovariables approach that is selecting macroeconomics factors which is first committed by Chen et. al. (1986) which then followed by other researchers who replicated Chen et. al. (1986) research. The other researchers use different macro variables in their research. One of the models which uses different macro variable from Chen et.al. (1986) is Elton, Gruber, May (1994) model. This research takes bottomside of model Elton et. al. (1994) by adding macro variable of gold price. This study wants to analyse the validity of APT to explain the change of share price at the Indonesian Stock Exchange by taking bottomside of Elton, Gruber, May (1994) model by adding gold price variable. This study covers four macro variables: interest of government long-term debt, inflation, exchange rate and gold price. These macro variables are tested in 25 liquid shares in Indonesian Stock Exchange to test the influence of these variables on the return share which means testing the validity of APT in Indonesian Stock Exchange.

2. Previous Research

The Arbitrage Pricing Theory is introduced by Ross (1976). The first researcher who used prespecifying macrovariables is Chen, Roll, Ross (1986). His research concludes that there is a significant relationship between term structure of interest rate, industrial production, bond risk premium, inflation, market return and return share. In the research done later, there are some research replicate CRR (1986) model with different results and there are also studies with different macroeconomics factors.

APT has been tested either in developed countries or in developing countries, but the results are different among the researchers. Beenstock & Chen (1988) conclude that there is a significant relationship between unanticipated increase interest, fuel & materials costs, money supply, retail price index and return share. Elton, Gruber and May (1994) conclude that changes in inflation rate, changes in the term structure of interest rates, changes the level of interest rates, changes in foreign exchange rates were influential to return share.

Groenewold and Fraser (1997) in Australia found that money supply, inflation and short term interest were influential to return share. In the Italian Stock Exchange, Panetta (2001) made share subdividing and got that unexpected term structure, unexpected changes in industrial production, unexpected inflation, unexpected changes in oil prices, the changes in the Lira/ Soviet Union dollar. Paavola (2006) studied 20 biggest shares in Russia and obtained a result that only unanticipated change in oil price had an effect on return share

Aziz et. al. (2005) in Karachi got an inflation surprise with a negative effect while a market index with a positive effect to return share. The used method is a regression with 2 phases. In Pakistan, Attaullah (2008) studied differently with CRR, namely regression with two phases methods. He used NLSUR (Non-Linier Seemingly Unrelated Regressions) method to estimate risk premia. The obtained result is that unexpected inflation, unexpected exchange rate, unexpected crude oil prices, unexpected trade balance are significant.

Ramadan (2012) studied in Jordania Stock Exchange. The result of his finding is the term structure of interest rates, risk premium, industrial production, money supply influential significant to return share. The effect of variables has been tested in varies industries.

In Indonesia, the results are also different among the researchers: Premananto and Madyan (2004) in Indonesian Stock Exchange (ISX) studied at manufacturing industry and its result showed that unexpected inflation, unexpected interest rate, unexpected exchange rate do not have an effect on return share while Arman (2008) in ISX obtained a result of surprise inflation and deposit rate that have negative significant influence while surprise number of money supplies, exchange rate, the growth of foreign invesment, economic growth have positive significant influence. Suartini and Mertha (2013) in ISX got a result of only Bank Indonesia rate which had an positive significant influence. Widodo (2007) got a result of surprise interest rate and exchange rate which have negative significant influence.

3. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Research Model

Following Elton, Gruber, May (1994) and using ordinary least square, the four variables are joined into linear regression model which is interest of government long term debt, inflation, exchange rate, gold price to test influence to stock return in the Indonesian Stock Exchange.

4. Hypotheses

This research has four hypotheses, they are:

H_1 : Interest of Government long term debt has a negative impact on return share

H_2 : Inflation has a negative impact on return share

H_3 : Exchange rate has a negative impact on return share

H_4 : Gold price has a negative impact on return share

5. Research Method

The study sample consists of the most liquid stock from the Indonesian Stock Exchange and which is available during the period 2009 - 2013 called LQ 45 and there were 25 Indonesian companies consistently enter LQ 45. Samples are taken only from the share which is liquid because the share commerce in Indonesian Stock Exchange is thin, meaning many shares are inactive. The quarterly closing prices of stocks of the sample firms were used in order to calculate the quarterly return of the industry portfolios. For this research we used pooled data for a period of five years. The macroeconomic variables (interest of government long term debt, inflation, exchange rate, gold price) are measured by the change in the values of these variables instead of the value itself. Its reason is because a change of macro variables is more correct compared to stock returns.

The research procedure consists of 2 phases of regression that is: 1) macro economic variable change regressed with return share in order to obtain share sensitivity to macro economic variable (β) of every company. 2) β obtained previously then regressed towards average return of the company. Looking at the macro economic condition aspect, it is necessary to take sensitivity into consideration because the majority of companies will experience the impact, only the sensitivity is different.

Regression for Phase 1

Below is an equality of regression for phase 1.

$$R_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_{i1}CLTG_t + \beta_{i2}CINF_t + \beta_{i3}CEXC_t + \beta_{i4}CGP_t + \varepsilon_t$$

R_{it} = return on the companies

β_0 = constant

β_i = sensitivity

CLTG = change in interest of government long term debt.

CINF = change in inflation

CEXC = change in exchange rate

CGP = change in gold price

ε_t = errors

Change in Interest of Government Long term Debt

Change in interest of government long term debt should be able to affect company return because the increase of the interest of government long term debt causes companies to issue obligation which necessarily give interest rate above the interest of government long term debt. A change at this variable can affect discount rate of the coming cash flow so that this matter will be responded by investors who cause a change in share price. In formulating the variable to measure influence of interest rate, must be considered the level of interest rate.

$$CLTG = \frac{LTG_t - LTG_{t-1}}{LTG_{t-1}}$$

CLTG = Change in interest of government long term debt.

LTG_t = interest of government long term debt in period of t

LTG_{t-1} = interest of government long term government debt in period of t-1

Change in Exchange Rate

The increase of the exchange rate causes investor of the capital market to benefit from that momentum by purchasing foreign currency and as a result make them sell their shares and transfer their fund to a foreign currency and as a result a lot of selling happen which cause the stock return to decrease.

$$CEXC = \frac{EXC_t - EXC_{t-1}}{EXC_{t-1}}$$

CEXC = change in exchange rate

EXC_t = exchange rate in period of t

EXC_{t-1} = exchange rate in period of t-1

Change in Inflation

Inflation can increase prices and also cause the government increase deposit interest rate then the investor of capital market transfer their fund to the Bank. Because there are many stock selling which cause the stock return to decrease.

$$CINF = \frac{INF_t - INF_{t-1}}{INF_{t-1}}$$

CINF = change in inflation

INF_t = inflation in period of t

INF_{t-1} = inflation in period of t-1

Change in Gold Price

Gold Price change can affect company return because if the price of gold increase, it can make investors to move their investment into the capital market because investment of gold is more solid compared to investment in the capital market so that it results in share price change in the capital market.

$$CGP = \frac{GLD_t - GLD_{t-1}}{GLD_{t-1}}$$

CGP = change in gold price

GLD_t = gold price in period of t

GLD_{t-1} = gold price in period of t-1

Below is an equality of regression for phase 2.

Regression for Phase 2

$$R_{it} = \lambda_0 + \lambda_{i1}Sens_CLTG_t + \lambda_{i2}Sens_CINF_t + \lambda_{i3}Sens_CEXC_t + \lambda_{i4}Sens_CGP_t + \varepsilon_t$$

R_{it} = average return on the companies

λ_0 = constant

λ = linear regression coefficient

Sens_CLTG = sensitivity in interest of government long term debt.

Sens_CINF = sensitivity in inflation

Sens_CEXC = sensitivity in exchange rate

Sens_CGP = sensitivity in gold price

ε_t = errors

Sample

The sample used to estimate returns models consists of all 2009 to 2013 years-firm that have data needed for calculating returns. The sample of companies listed in LQ 45 for the time period of 2009 -2013 is shown in table 1

Sample required at first phase regression is 125 datas from 25 companies of year 2009 up to 2013 with data quarterly. While sample required at second phase regression is 25 samples. Below this table presents the companies in the sample study, there are:

Table 1. Sample of Companies Stock Names Listed in LQ 45

AALI	ANTM	ASII	BBCA	BBRI
BDMN	BMRI	BRPT	EARTH	ENRG
GGRM	INCO	INDF	INTP	KIJA
KLBF	LPKR	LSIP	PGAS	PTBA
TLKM	UNSP	UNTR	UNVR	TINS

Source of Data

The data source for the interest of government long term debt, inflation, exchange rate are obtained from Bank Indonesia, the data for the gold price are obtained from Badan Pusat Statistik Indonesia while the data in share price are obtained from the Indonesia Capital Market Directory. The data for stock return are obtained from the data for the processed share price, which are obtained from the Indonesian Capital Market Directory.

6. Result of Research

Before committing to the next hypothesis examination after the model is made, the classic assumption is examined. to ensure that model is built, it must have the character of Best Linear Unbiased Estimation.

- **Normality**

Errors that are estimated by residu is assumed to follow the normal distribution. This assumption is very important to be fulfilled for hypothesis examination validity by using t and F test statistic. To know whether the errors are distributed normally, the two approaches can be used, that is graphic method and normality test.

Table 2. Normality Test

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Unstandardized Residual	.137	25	.200*

The result by using SPSS p-value 0.200 is obtained (Kolmogorov Smirnov test). This value is greater than 0.05, so it has a normal distribution.

- **Non Heteroscedasticity Test**

The following assumption that the errors have the same variance or non heteroskedastisity. Some test statistics can be used to test assumption non heteroskedastisity among others is Glejser's test. To see the significance in the SPSS output can be seen from the significant value. If the value of significant is greater than 0.05, it can be expressed that there are homoscedasticity assumption violation.

The calculation of Glejser's model can be done with SPSS with the following result :

Table 3. Non Heteroscedasticity Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.025	.006		4.195	.000
Sens_Change in Interest of Government Long term Debt	-.006	.009	-.681	-.657	.519
Sens_Change in Inflation	-.025	.015	-3.565	-1.732	.099
Sens_Change in Exchange Rate	-.004	.002	-3.818	-1.683	.108
Sens_Change in Gold Price	.013	.006	.943	1.981	.061

a. Dependent Variable: ABS_RES

From the above table, it can be concluded that all independent variables have p-value greater than 0.05 so there are no heteroscedasticity.

- **Non Autocorrelation Test**

The next assumption is non autocorrelation assumption. This assumption express that errors between observations do not interact.

To test this assumption, we can use the Durbin Watson statistic test.

Criterion Test

If the Ho hypothesis have no positive autocorrelation, then :

$$DW < DL \quad : \text{Reject Ho}$$

$$DU < DW < 4 - dU \quad : \text{Accepted Ho}$$

$$DL < DW < DU \quad : \text{The test is inconclusive}$$

If Ho hypothesis have no negative autocorrelation then :

$$DW > 4 - DL \quad : \text{Reject H0}$$

$$DU < DW < 4 - dU \quad : \text{Accepted H0}$$

$$4 - DU < DW < 4 - DL \quad : \text{The test is inconclusive}$$

Table 4. Non Autocorrelation Test

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
.743 ^a	.551	.462	.03975126	1.772

The result of calculation by using SPSS, the value of DW statistic = 1.77 can be obtained. While from the Durbin Watson table for $n = 25$ dan $k = 4$ is obtained $DL = 0.835$ dan $DU = 1.521$. The value of DW is between $DU < DW < 4 - dU$ or $1.521 < DW < 2.479$ so that it can be concluded that null hypothesis is accepted then it is stated that there is no autocorrelation.

- **Non Multicollinearity Test**

Furthermore there is additional assumption, that is non multicollinearity. In the classical assumption of Gauss Markov, he does not mention non multicollinearity assumption. In the independent variable selection regression analysis is assumed that there is no correlation between independent variables. To detect the violation of the assumption, we can use Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) statistic. If the value of VIF bigger than 15, there is a violation of non multicollinearity assumption.

Table 5. Non Multicollinearity Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Sens_Change in Interest of Government Long term Debt [X ₁]	.034	29.299
Sens_Change in Inflation [X ₂]	.009	115.557
Sens_Change in Exchange Rate [X ₃]	.007	140.224
Sens_Change in Gold Price [X ₄]	.162	6.181

The result of the SPSS calculation showed that only Sens_Change in Gold Price variable [X₄] that the value of VIF is less than 15. This shows only Sens_Change in Gold Price [X₄] which has no strong correlation with other variables. Looking at this condition, we can see that there is a violation of multicollinierity. But the multicollinierity does not always cause a problem as long as the model obtained is the best model. In other words, if we overcome multicollinierity, but logically the model obtained is not better, therefore the assumption can be ignored.

The result of the examined normality, non heteroscedasticity, and non autocorrelation assumption, is concluded fulfilled. Therefore hypothesis test with F and t statistic test can be done.

7. The Result of Hypotheses Testing

From Table 6 we can see that R square which obtained is reative high, that is 0,551 or 55,1 % which means that interest of government long term debt, inflation, exchange rate and gold price can explain return 55,2% while the rest can be explained by other variables which is not research.

Table 6. R Square Value

R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
.551	.462	.03975126	1.772

The result of calculation with SPSS is presented as follows :

Table 7. Overall Test (F Test)

Model	Sum of Squares	d.f	mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	.039	4	.010	6.146	.002 ^a
Residual	.032	20	.002		
Total	.070	24			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Sens_CGP, Sens_CINF, Sens_CLTG, Sens_CEXC

b. Dependent Variable: Return

Table above shows that $F = 6.146$ or $p\text{-value} = 0.002$ less than 0.05 , which means there is at least a significant independent variable relating to return variable.

Table 8. Partial Test (t Test)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.036	.012		2.897	.009
Sens_Change in Interest of Government Long term Debt [X ₁]	-.024	.018	-1.065	-1.314	.204
Sens_Change in Inflation [X ₂]	-.110	.030	-5.971	-3.709	.001
Sens_Change in Exchange Rate [X ₃]	-.016	.005	-5.691	-3.209	.004
Sens_Change in Gold Price [X ₄]	.022	.013	.630	1.693	.106

The p-value that is less than 5% for Sens_Change in Inflation [X₂] and Sens_Change in Exchange Rate [X₃] indicates that these variables have a significant effect on the return. While Sens_Change in Interest of Government Long term Debt [X₁] and Sens_Change in Gold Price [X₄] do not have a significant effect on the return.

But the insignificant variables does not mean that the variables must be eliminated from the model but only the influence is relatively less than the other variables. The insignificant of independent variables may be caused by the violation of the assumption. One of the methods that can be used to overcome violation is the Ridge Regression method.

Ridge Regression

The result of Ridge Regression analysis is 0.171 (prob level) indicates that there is none significant independent variable that influence return variable. Besides that the R^2 only 0.264 far less than the beginning model ($R^2 = 0.551$). So that previously model is better compared to Ridge Regression Model.

Based on SPSS output is obtained a regression model as follows :

$$\widehat{Return} = 0.036 - 0.024Sens_CInterest\ of\ Government\ Long\ Term\ Debt - 0.110Sens_CInflation - 0.016 \times Sens_CExchange\ Rate + 0.022Sens_CGold\ Price$$

8. The Results of Hypotheses Testing

8.1. Results of Testing H_1

Based on the table the result of sample LQ 45 shows that the p-value for the interest of government long term debt is 0,204 > dari 0,05 which means it is not significant and the coefficient sign is negative. The increase of the interest of government long term debt causes companies to issue obligation which necessarily give interest rate above the interest of government long term debt. If companies cannot afford to increase their sale, they will be responded negatively by investors. This matter can happen because investors notice that an increase in interest rate becomes a burden for the companies.

8.2. Results of Testing H_2

The result of sample LQ 45 shows that p-value for the inflation is 0,001 less than 0,005 meaning significant and the sign of its coefficient is negative. Inflation can increase prices and also cause the government increase deposit interest rate then the investor of capital market transfer their fund to the Bank. Because there are many stock selling which cause decrease in stock return.

8.3. Results of Testing H_3

The result of sample LQ 45 shows that p-value for the exchange rate is 0,004 less than 0,005 meaning significant and the sign of its coefficient is negative. The registered companies at ISX owe abroad and the manufacturing industries import a lot of raw materials from other countries. So conversion value change will have an impact on a cash stream so that this matter will be responded by investors who cause a change in share price. Besides that, the increase of the exchange rate causes investor of the capital market to benefit from that momentum by purchasing foreign currency and as a result make them sell their shares and transfer their fund to a foreign currency and as a result a lot of selling happen which cause the share price to decrease.

8.4. Results of Testing H_4

The result of LQ 45 shows that p-value for the gold price is 0,106 greater than 0,05 meaning not significant and the sign of coefficient is positive. Other than investing in stock, people in Indonesia are also interested in investing in gold. There are several benefits when interesting in gold that is not a very big amount is needed. In the better economic condition, people will tend to add their investment in buying gold, so they added gold in their investment portofolio. Economic matters during the research period showed growth every year. Increase in economic growth will increase the income of the Indonesia inhabitants. The income per capita of the Indonesian inhabitant increase 1% to 7% percent per year (Statistics Indonesia, 2013.) With the increase of income the people have the opportunity to decrease the risk by adding portfolio investment in gold.

9. Summary and Concluding Remarks

The results of statistical test are as follows:

- Interest of government long-term debt has an insignificant influence on return.
- Inflation has a negative significant influence on return
- Exchange rate has a negative significant influence on return
- Gold price has an insignificant influence on return

From the above result, it can be concluded that Arbitrage Pricing Theory in Indonesian Stock Exchange is supported. Result of regression indicate that macro economic factors have the ability to explain share price change. The model can be used to predict the future outcomes because has 0.551 R-square value. Macro economic factors need to be considered because they influence the share change or the return of the companies. The government or the companies need to anticipate the macro economic change which is unfavorable. For further research, we propose to use a different methodology to calculate the sensitivity and also to add other macro-economic variables to produce a result of a higher R-square in order to obtain a better model.

References

- Arman, Agus. (2008). Surprise Faktor Makroekonomi Sebagai Penjelas Perubahan Return Pasar Saham di Bursa Efek Indonesia. *National Conference on Management Research 2008*. Makasar, 27 November 2008, ISBN:979-442-242-8
- Attaulah, Ali. (2008). Macroeconomic Factors, the APT and the Istanbul Stock Market. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics* ISSN 1450-2887 Issue 22 EuroJournals Publishing Inc.
- Chen, Nai-Fu, Roll, Richard R., & Ross, Stephen A. (1986). Economic Forces and the Stock Market. *Journal of Business*, 59(3), 383-404.
- Chen, S.J., & Jordan, B.D. (1993). Some Empirical Tests in the Arbitrage Pricing Theory: Macrovariables vs. Derived Factors. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 17(1), 65-89.
- Elton, Edwin J., Gruber, Martin J. & Mei, Jianping. (1994). Cost of Capital Using Arbitrage Pricing Theory: A Case Study of Nine New York Utilities. *Financial Markets, Institution and Instruments*, 3, 46-73.
- Fabio, Panetta. 2001. The Stability of the Relation Between the Stock Market and Macroeconomic Forces. *Temi di discussione (Economic Working Papers)*. Bank of Italy, Economic Research Department.
- Groenewold, N., & Fraser, P. (1997). Share Prices and Macroeconomic Factors. *Journal of Business and Accounting*, 24 (9), 1367-1381.
- Murtianingsih. (2012). Variabel Ekonomi Makro & Indeks Harga Saham Gabungan. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Akuntansi*. Vol.1, No. 3, Desember 2012.
- Paavola, Mauri. (2006). Tests of the Arbitrage Pricing Theory: Using Macroeconomic Variables in the Russian Equity Market. *Bachelor's Thesis*. Department of Business Administration Section of Accounting and Finance, Lappeenranta University of Technology.
- Premananto, Gancar Candra; Madyan, Muhammad. (2004). Perbandingan Keakuratan Capital Aset Pricing Model dan Arbitrage Pricing Theory dalam Memprediksi Tingkat Pendapatan Saham Industri Manufaktur Sebelum dan Semasa Krisis Ekonomi. *Jurnal Penelitian Dinamika Sosial*, Vol. 5 No. 2 Agustus 2004: 125-139.
- Ramadan, Imad Z. (2012). The Validity of the Arbitrage Pricing Theory in the Jordanian Stock Market. *International Journal of Economics and Finance* 4.5, 177-185.
- Suartini, Ni Kadek Ayu; Mertha, I Made. (2013). Perbandingan CAPM dengan APT dalam Memprediksi Return Saham. *E-Journal Universitas Udayana*, Vol. 2, No.3, Maret 2013.
- Widodo, Purwanto. (2007). Pengaruh Pergerakan Variabel Ekonomi Makro Terhadap Return IHSG dan LQ45. *Jurnal Madani Edisi I/ Mei 2007*.

APPENDIX

Data (macro economic sensitivity obtained from phase 1 regression)

No.	Perush	Return	Sens_CLTG	Sens_CINF	Sens_CEXC	Sens_CGP
1	AALI	0.06112	-0.19000	-0.32000	0.58000	-0.03000
2	ANTM	0.09471	0.22000	-0.11000	-1.60000	-0.26000
3	ASII	0.06917	0.03000	-0.35000	-1.90000	0.47000
4	BBCA	0.06087	0.06000	0.10000	-1.30000	0.11000
5	BBRI	0.04105	0.11000	-0.01000	-1.34000	-0.28000
6	BDMN	0.02522	0.19000	0.03000	-2.15000	-0.65000
7	BMRI	0.08134	-0.18000	0.01000	-1.89000	-0.36000
8	BRPT	0.02682	-0.05000	-0.48000	-0.87000	-1.52000
9	BUMI	0.01044	-0.02000	-0.32000	-3.41000	-1.25000
10	ENRG	0.16280	1.56000	-1.93000	-4.24000	-5.30000
11	GGRM	0.16010	-0.14000	-0.37000	-2.64000	-0.50000
12	INCO	0.04183	-0.25000	-0.22000	-0.64000	-1.24000
13	INDF	0.12688	-0.10000	-0.14000	-2.84000	-0.77000
14	INTP	0.08990	0.30000	-0.18000	-1.69000	-0.32000
15	KIJA	0.10520	0.54000	-0.52000	-2.04000	-1.17000
16	KLBF	0.11797	-0.03000	-0.09000	-1.82000	-0.00400
17	LPKR	0.02054	0.46000	0.14000	-0.75000	0.16000
18	LSIP	0.05272	-0.28000	-0.37000	-1.01000	-0.39000
19	PGAS	0.19472	-1.07000	-0.58000	-3.03000	-0.55000
20	PTBA	0.03796	-0.26000	-0.12000	-1.94000	-0.35000
21	TLKM	-0.00950	0.09000	0.19000	-1.73000	0.63000
22	UNSP	-0.02915	11.82000	-14.79000	94.87000	4.61000
23	UNTR	0.09880	0.17000	-0.33000	-0.30000	0.02000
24	UNVR	0.07105	0.73000	0.09000	-1.89000	-0.05000
25	TINS	0.05272	-0.75000	-0.02000	-0.22000	-1.37000

Ridge Regression Model

Analysis of Variance Section for k = 0.050000					
Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-Ratio	Prob Level
Intercept	1	0.125	0.125		
Model	4	0.019	0.005	1.789	0.171
Error	20	0.052	0.003		
Total(Adjusted)	24	0.070	0.003		
Mean of Dependent	0.071				
Root Mean Square Error	0.051				
R-Squared	0.264				
Coefficient of Variation	0.721				